

An improved, practical and efficient method for the synthesis of novel *N*-chloro derivatives using calcium hypochlorite

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Abstract : The developed method was employed in the synthesis of medicinally important compounds and intermediates in the organic synthesis. Herein we report a variety of novel *N*-chloro derivatives of benzisoxazole, benzimidazoles and several other *N*-chloro derivatives using 1.2 equivalents of calcium hypochlorite. The process does not require any additives like acids or bases and produced moderate to excellent yields of desired products under mild conditions.

Keywords : Synthesis, calcium hypochlorite, *N*-chloro derivatives, *N*-chloro benzisoxazole.

Introduction

N-Chloro compounds were found to be versatile reagents and starting materials for the synthesis of various chemical and biologically important compounds¹. Many of these derivatives are known to possess antimicrobial activity and reduced potential for the development of antibiotic resistance². *N*-Halo derivatives have their own applications in polymer chemistry³. In recent years, various improved methods were reported using chlorine gas⁴, lead tetra acetate⁵, oxone and sodium chloride⁶, phosphorous pentachloride⁷, sulphur oxy chloride⁸, hypochlorous acid⁹, sodium hypochlorite^{1b}, tertiary butyl hypochlorite², trichloroisocyanuric acid (TCCA)¹⁰, Ca(OCl)₂/Al₂O₃/AcOH¹¹ and *N*-chloro succinamide¹² as oxidants for the chlorination of amides and amines under various pH conditions. Apart from the reported methods, majority of them suffering from either acidic or basic conditions, possess a limited substrate scope, involve the laborious workup procedure, removal of byproduct from the reaction mixture makes the process inconvenient and hazardous oxidizing agents makes the process challenging¹³. Hence, mild, economic, easy to use and environmentally safe method is required. Recent work from our laboratory described that the selective oxidation of alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds using calcium hypochlorite with TEMPO which has clearly demonstrated that the addition of acid or base is not required when calcium hypochlorite was used as an oxidant. The advan-

tages of calcium hypochlorite over the other chlorinated reagents were also discussed¹⁴. Reconsidering the use of calcium hypochlorite as an oxidizing agent, here by we report the chlorination of the variety of amines and amides using calcium hypochlorite as an oxidant and chlorinating agent. The developed method works under mild reaction conditions and can be used for the preparative scale using 6-fluoro-3-(piperidin-4-yl)benzisoxazole as a standard substrate under metal free and simple reaction conditions (Table 1).

Experimental

General remarks :

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 400 and 100 MHz respectively. Chemical shifts are quoted in parts per million (δ) relative to TMS or CHCl₃ (residual chloroform in CDCl₃). IR spectra were recorded at Shimadzu Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer. Materials obtained from commercial suppliers were used without further purification (Sigma-Aldrich, Merck, AcrRs and from local vendors).

General procedure for the N-chlorination (Table 2, Entry 1-16) :

Charged 1 mmol substrate **1a-16a** (1 mmol) into acetonitrile (2 mL) then cooled to 0 °C, slowly added 1.2 mmol of calcium hypochlorite within ten to twenty minutes. Reaction was monitored by TLC until the completion of reaction. Filtered the salts, washed the salts with

acetonitrile, dried and concentrated under vacuum. Crude residue was purified by column chromatography to give desire product.

Methyl-1-chloro-7-methyl-2-propyl-1H-benzof[d]imidazole-5-carboxylate (Table 2, **5b**) : Obtained **8b** with 88% yield as white solid. m.p. 105–108 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : 7.98 (1H, s), 7.80 (1H, s), 3.95 (3H, s), 2.98 (2H, t), 2.65 (3H, s), 1.94 (2H, m), 1.09 (3H, t); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : 167.5, 157.2, 143.4, 135.0, 129.9, 125.3, 125.0, 109.4, 52.3, 29.3, 21.23, 16.3, 14.0; MS (ESI) *m/z* Calcd. 266.1, Found : 267.2.

1'-Chloro-1,7'-dimethyl-2'-propyl-1H,1'H-2,5'-bibenzof[d]imidazole (Table 2, **6b**) : Quenched the reaction mass in ice cold water and then stirred for 2 h. Solid was filtered, and washed with chilled water and dried the product to give desire product **9b** with 86% yield as pale yellow color solid. m.p. 140–142 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : 7.85 (1H, m), 7.69 (1H, s), 7.48 (1H, d), 7.43 (1H, m), 7.36 (2H, m), 3.92 (3H, s), 3.01 (2H, t), 2.71 (3H, s), 1.97 (2H, m), 1.11 (3H, t); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : 156.1, 154.3, 143.1, 141.0, 136.8, 135.4, 130.4, 125.4, 124.9, 122.9, 122.6, 119.8, 109.8, 109.7, 108.6, 32.0, 31.4, 29.3, 21.3, 17.2, 16.4, 14.0; MS (ESI) *m/z* Calcd. 338.13, Found : 339.2.

N-Chloro-N-ethyl aniline (Table 2, **7b**) : Obtained *N*-chloro compounds are highly unstable, immediately undergoes a rearrangement on aromatic ring. Crude residue was purified by column chromatography to give desire

product **10b** with 79% yield with rearranged product as yellow color liquid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : 7.25–7.12 (5H, m), 3.58 (2H, q), 1.3 (3H, m); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : 144.3, 129.3, 127.9, 119.0, 117.9, 111.2, 45.1, 14.8; MS (ESI) *m/z* Calcd. 155.05, Found : 156.13.

N-Butyl-N, 4-dichloroaniline (Table 2, **8b**) : ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : 7.13 (2H, dd), 6.61 (2H, dd), 3.14 (2H, t), 1.67–1.42 (4H, m), 0.98 (2H, m), 0.98 (3H, t); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) : 128.7, 127.8, 111.7, 43.6, 31.7, 22.8, 14.2; MS (ESI) *m/z* Calcd. 217.05, Found : 218.1.

N, 3-Dichloro-N-dodecylaniline (Table 2, **9b**) : Obtained **10b** with 78% yield as yellow color liquid. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : 7.29–7.188 (Ar-3H, m), 3.27 (2H, t), 1.52 (2H, m), 1.47–1.18 (Aliphatic 18H, m), 0.82 (3H, t); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) : 143.3, 131.0, 129.1, 125.5, 124.6, 123.6, 47.8, 32.1, 31.1, 30.0, 29.7, 29.5, 26.9, 22.8, 14.3.

Results and discussion

Derivatives of benzisoxazole possess a wide range of biological applications¹⁵, keeping in view the importance of benzisoxazole, it was a model substrate for current study focus on the possibility of *N*-chlorination reaction with calcium hypochlorite under mild reaction conditions (Table 1). This procedure is very simple, mild, clean, and works efficiently without any additives and produces 96% yield with excellent purity (Table 1, Entry 3). Due to its high efficiency our initial studies were focused on

Table 1. *N*-Chlorination of 6-fluoro-3-(piperidin-4-yl)benzisoxazole using various solvents and Ca(OCl)₂

Entry	Oxidant	Solvent	Time (h)	Yield ^{a,b}	Entry	Oxidant	Solvent	Time (h)	Yield ^{a,b}
1	2.0	Acetonitrile	0.5	96 ^{a,b}	7	1.2	Acetone	6	42 ^{a,b}
2	1.5	Acetonitrile	0.5	95 ^{a,b}	8	1.2	Toluene	12	N.R. ^{a,b}
3	1.2	Acetonitrile	1	96 ^{b,c}	9	1.2	Hexane	12	N.R. ^{a,b}
4	1.0	Acetonitrile	3	80 ^{a,b}	10	1.2	Chloroform	4	74 ^{a,b}
5	1.2	DCM	3	84 ^{a,b}	11	1.2	Methanol	4.5	70 ^{a,b}
6	1.2	Ethyl acetate	6	30 ^{a,b}	12	1.2	DMF	2	50 ^{a,b}

Note : N.R – no reaction. Eq - equivalent, ^aone mmol substrate used; ^bisolated yields; ^c5 g (mmol) of **1**, 1.2 eq. of Ca(OCl)₂, acetonitrile 25 mL.

optimizing the suitable solvent system and the amount of oxidizing agent using 1 mmol of compound **1** with the various solvents such as acetonitrile, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, acetone, toluene, hexane, chloroform, methanol and DMF. Among these acetonitrile was found to be the better solvent system (Scheme 1, Entry 3 and Table 1) which gave >99% conversion and 96% isolated yield as compared to other solvents shown in Scheme 1 and Table 1. This is the first ever report on the synthesis of derivative of *N*-chloro benzoisoxazole **1** and the crystal structure of compound **1** as we have discussed in our recent article¹⁶.

The scope of the oxidation system was extended to other medicinally important molecule like derivatives of isatin (Table 2, **1a**) which are reported to possess antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antitumoral, anticonvulsant and sedative-hypnotic activity¹⁷. Under the above optimized conditions we have obtained the corresponding *N*-chloro derivative of isatin in 94% of isolated yield (Table 2, **1b**). Next, we have chosen the molecules having biologically important (piperidone and morpholine)¹⁸ and starting intermediates for the many of the medicinal important compounds (Table 2, **2b** and **3b**) in the present study respective desired *N*-chloro derivatives were obtained in 88 and 92% of yield. The scope of this study is further extended to other biologically important compounds

namely derivatives of benzotriazole (Table 2, **4a**) which are used as the chemotherapeutic agents, antimicrobial, analgesic, anticancer activities¹⁹ and used as chlorinating reagent for the chlorination of various amides²⁰. The corresponding *N*-chloro derivatives of triazoles were obtained in 67% of isolated yield (Table 2, **4b**). Benzimidazole derivatives are medicinally important compounds²¹ and these are key intermediates (Table 2, **5a** and **6a**) in the synthesis of antihypertensive drug i.e. telmisartan. Derivatives of benzimidazole which were contains both electron withdrawing (ester) and donating (methyl) groups (Table 2, **5a**) and also activating groups like aryl (Table 2, **6a**) gave the corresponding *N*-chloro derivatives in excellent yields (Table 2, **5b** and **6b**). The scope of the oxidation method was further extended to compounds having aryl alkyl amines containing electron-pumping and electron deactivating groups (Table 1, Entry 7–12). Produced *N*-chloro compounds are highly unstable, immediately undergoes a rearrangement on aromatic ring (Entry **7b–9b**)²². However to obtain the *N*-chloro compounds from aromatic anilines we were synthesized and attempted several substituent's like *N*-ethyl aniline, 4-chloro-*N*-butyl anilines to carry out the reaction. These compounds are isolated with the rearranged products (Entry **7b** and **8b**) and it was confirmed by ¹H NMR. But long alkyl chain with *meta* chloro substituent (Entry **9b**) produced

Table 2. *N*-Chlorination of various amines and amides

Note : Structures of the products were determined from their spectroscopic (IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and MS) data.

in good yield without any rearranged product. In a similar manner when other electron withdrawing groups such as nitro, cyano were present, no reaction took place even in prolonged reaction time. From above all experiments it is clear that reaction rates of amides are more as compared with amines (Table 1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the current study involves the use of calcium hypochlorite as an oxidant in acetonitrile solvent which could oxidize selectively a variety of amines and amides to the corresponding *N*-chloro derivatives. All the reactions were carried out at room temperature without affecting the other existing functionalities such as nitrogen, double bonds and the sensitive groups like esters. Significantly, present protocol does not require any additives. Currently all the isolated *N*-chloro derivatives are under biological screening which is going on in our laboratory.

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